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**INTERNATIONAL REFERENCE GROUP
ON GREAT LAKES POLLUTION
FROM LAND USE ACTIVITIES**

GLC Z2222 11

**INTERNATIONAL
JOINT
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75-007

PROCEEDINGS

SANDUSKY RIVER BASIN SYMPOSIUM

MAY 2 - 3, 1975

TIFFIN, OHIO

Co-sponsors: Heidelberg College

Bowling Green State University

The publication of the proceedings of the Sandusky River Symposium was carried out as part of the efforts of the Pollution from Land Use Activities Reference Group, an organization of the International Joint Commission, established under the Canada-U.S. Great Lakes Water Quality Agreement of 1972. Funding for the printing of the document was provided through the U.S. Environmental Protection Agency. Findings and conclusions are those of the authors and do not necessarily reflect the views of the Reference Group or its recommendations to the Commission.

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MAY 2-3, 1975

Tiffin, Ohio

SPONSORED BY

HEIDELBERG COLLEGE
Tiffin, Ohio 44883

BOWLING GREEN STATE UNIVERSITY
Bowling Green, Ohio 43403

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PREFACE

The Sandusky River Basin Symposium, held at Heidelberg College in Tiffin, Ohio and jointly sponsored by Heidelberg and Bowling Green State University, brought together more than 150 persons engaged in environmental research, monitoring, and management, both in the Sandusky Basin and from surrounding areas. The program scope and the purpose of the symposium indicated:

A considerable amount of ecological research and monitoring activity is taking place within the Sandusky River and Bay areas. The research ranges from studies of the geology, hydrology, and soils of the basin and bay to measurements of the biological and chemical characteristics of the river and bay. In this conference, the individuals who are involved in the entire scope of the above research efforts, as well as those involved with water quality management within the basin, will present their research results and current management practices.

The purpose of this conference is to provide an opportunity for the scientists engaged in ecological research and those engaged in management to exchange detailed information that will aid both in future work. The conference should also provide useful information to individuals working in other river basin studies and anyone interested in the relationships between ecosystem research and river basin management.

The symposium was successful in attaining many of these objectives, and the diversity and detail of environment-related studies underway in the Sandusky Basin and Bay areas was impressive. The historical perspectives of this region, as brought forth in papers by Trautman, Forsyth, and Stuckey, created a useful foundation. The keynote address by Cummins, extending stream ecosystem theory to larger rivers, had significant impact on both ecosystem concepts and management applications. The contributions of personnel in governmental agencies provided an overview of programs within which environmental planning and management take place.

The program of the symposium has been reproduced in the table of contents. The proceedings differ from the symposium in that the many excellent color slides, which potentiated the presentations, necessarily have been replaced by tabular data. Both these quantitative and qualitative presentations will aid future studies in this basin and other areas.

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ABSTRACT

EFFECTS OF ADVANCED WASTE TREATMENT AND FLOW
AUGMENTATION ON WATER QUALITY DURING LOW STREAM FLOWS

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During periods of low stream flow, especially in summer and fall, algal growth often reaches nuisance levels as judged by aesthetic considerations and data from oxygen monitors. As stream flow decreases, nutrient concentrations increase in stream stretches below sewage treatment plants, the travel-time increases (i.e. the river becomes lake like), and turbidity associated with inorganic sediment decreases. These, and possibly other factors, provide conditions that support the algal growth. Nutrient removal at sewage plants and flow augmentation from upground reservoirs may be effective in reducing this problem.

Comparison of diurnal oxygen fluctuations and stream flow at three continuous water quality monitors in the basin illustrate the effectiveness of runoff events in diminishing oxygen fluctuations. During the drought periods of July, 1974, flow augmentation releases from Killdeer Reservoir were sufficient to reduce oxygen fluctuations at the Tymochtee station. This effect accompanied the arrival of the flood front and preceded by three days the actual arrival of water from the reservoir.

During June-Sept., 1974, nutrient and chlorophyll concentrations were measured in the basin. The study area bracketed four point source inputs. Phosphorous concentrations increased sharply below each treatment plant but both concentration and flux decreased with passage downstream. At a given station no obvious correlation between phosphorous and chlorophyll was apparent. Physical characteristics of the stream, such as low-head dams and sections with high fall rates, did influence chlorophyll levels.

Two of the municipalities have instituted nutrient removal programs and the effects of these on nutrient and chlorophyll levels along the stream will be investigated in the summers of 1975 and 1976.

EFFECTS OF ADVANCED WASTE TREATMENT AND FLOW AUGMENTATION ON WATER QUALITY DURING LOW STREAM FLOWS

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INTRODUCTION

Often the daily minimum concentration of dissolved oxygen in streams drops as streamflow decreases. This is particularly true during the late summer and fall periods when water temperatures are high and the solubility of oxygen is low. When designing a sewage treatment plant, one goal is to be able to produce an effluent which will not result in water quality violations, as long as the streamflow exceeds a certain value. In Ohio, water quality standards are applicable whenever the flows exceed the annual minimum seven-day average flow that has a recurrence frequency of once in ten years (Ohio Environmental Protection Agency, 1975). Determining the maximum organic loading allowable for a sewage treatment plant involves determining the assimilative capacity of the stream during periods of late summer, low-flow conditions (Thomann, 1972; Cahill et al, 1975).

As mentioned in the introductory paper in this symposium, most of the oxygen violations in the Sandusky River (i.e., instances when the dissolved oxygen [D.O.] drops below 4.0 mg/l) are associated with diurnal oxygen fluctuations. This indicates that the metabolism of photosynthetic plants, rather than heterotrophic bacteria, is a major factor in determining the oxygen concentrations in the stream. Since the Sandusky River essentially lacks rooted aquatic plants, attached algae and/or phytoplankton are apparently responsible for the diurnal oxygen variations.

When constant loading of organic matter from a sewage treatment plant is the cause of low D.O. values, the relationship between D.O. and streamflow

can be explained, in part, in terms of a decreasing dilution of the organic wastes as the streamflow decreases. When algae are the cause of the low D.O. values, similar D.O./streamflow relationships occur as for organic loading, but the explanation is less clear-cut. Do algal concentrations increase as streamflow decreases, and if so, why? As stream flow decreases, do the physical changes associated with velocity and surface/volume ratios change in such a way as to decrease reaeration rates? Does the water mainly provide a "buffer" for a relatively stable benthic algal population so that as streamflow decreases, "buffer" capacity decreases? Our research is primarily directed toward the first of these three possibilities.

Three reasons why algal populations might increase as streamflow decreases would be that: (1) phosphorus concentrations increase, (2) the sediment concentrations decrease, thereby increasing the penetration of light, and (3) the time for algal growth increases greatly because of streamflow/time-of-travel relationships.

We have ample evidence to indicate that all of these effects occur within the Sandusky Basin. Figure 1a shows the relationship between the concentrations of total phosphorus and streamflow at a collection station a short distance downstream from a sewage treatment plant. As would be expected, when the streamflow decreases in the low flow range, the concentration of phosphorus increases, since there is less stream water to dilute the rather constant phosphorus inputs from the sewage treatment plant.

The plot in figure 1a also shows that the total phosphorus concentration increases as flow increases in the high flow ranges. This is a consequence of the increased sediment concentrations present during surface runoff events. Much phosphorus is adsorbed to the sediment. Figure 1b shows the

Figure 1. Patterns of concentrations of total phosphorous (A) and suspended solids (B) as a function of streamflow at the stream gage below Upper Sandusky, Ohio. Flows are expressed as the log (base 10) of the stream flow in liters per second. Includes data collected between June 1969 and November 1974. Unpublished data, Heidelberg College River Studies Laboratory.

relationship between suspended sediments and flow at the same station. The concentrations of suspended sediments are lowest during periods of low flows. This results in increasing transparency of the water as flow decreases.

Figure 2 presents some data showing the relationship between time-of-travel in the stream and streamflow, for several distances downstream from the Bucyrus sewage treatment plant. Normally these kinds of data are presented on log-log plots. The linear plots of figure 2 emphasize the large increases in time-of-travel which occur as stream flow decreases, particularly in the low flow ranges. The curves depict the river becoming "lake-like" as the flow decreases.

If it is deemed important to attempt to control water-quality effects associated with algae in rivers, an understanding of the interrelationships among streamflow, algal growth and diurnal oxygen fluctuations would be useful. In the Sandusky River, as well as other streams in Northwestern Ohio, attempts to prevent the development of nuisance levels of algae could include: (1) providing phosphorus removal at domestic sewage treatment plants and (2) providing increased streamflow during periods of low streamflow, using water stored in off-stream, upground reservoirs. Several of these reservoirs have been constructed as part of the Northwestern Ohio Development Plan (Ohio Department of Natural Resources, 1967).

Our approach in studying management options related to controlling algae in the Sandusky River Basin is direct. We will be measuring chlorophyll and nutrient concentrations in the river prior to and following removal of phosphorus at domestic sewage treatment plants in the basin. Also, during periods of low streamflow water will be released from the Killdeer Reservoir in the Tymochtee Basin. These releases can significantly

Figure 2 Time-of-travel of water in the Sandusky River in the river stretch downstream 0.56, 1.42, and 2.83 miles from the sewage treatment plant at Bucyrus, Ohio. At this station flows of 3.8 cfs are exceeded 80% of the time. Unpublished data, Heidelberg College River Studies Laboratory.

augment flows both in Tymochtee Creek and in the Sandusky below its confluence with Tymochtee Creek. Both of the above "manipulations" of the stream system have been made possible through cooperative research-planning with the Ohio Environmental Protection Agency and the Ohio Department of Natural Resources.

This report contains the preliminary findings of the first year of a three year study. During the first year, none of the municipalities in the basin utilized phosphorus removal procedures at their sewage treatment plants. For the second and third years of study, phosphorus removal procedures will be in effect.

Hynes (1970) has reviewed many of the factors which can affect the growth of phytoplankton in rivers. The difficulties of including algal growth and metabolism in oxygen models for rivers are noted by Thomam (1972).

METHODS

Three samples per week were collected at each of 29 collection stations located along the Sandusky River or its tributaries. All collections were made from bridges using buckets lowered by rope. Field measurements included dissolved oxygen and temperature. All samples were delivered to the laboratory within 6 hours of sample collection. Upon arrival, the samples were immediately divided into four portions, one for *in vivo* chlorophyll analysis, one for filtration through a glass fiber filter for subsequent acetone extraction and chlorophyll determination, one for filtration through 0.45 μ membrane filters for analysis of dissolved nutrients in the filtrate, and one for additional analyses, including total phosphorus, suspended solids and conductivity. The study extended from June 3 to October 9, 1974.

Both total phosphorus and soluble orthophosphate were measured using the single reagent automated method, as described in Methods for Analysis

of Water and Wastes (U.S. Environmental Protection Agency, 1971). Suspended solids and conductivities were also measured according to procedures described in the above manual. See Baker and Kramer (1976) for further descriptions of the analytical procedures used in our laboratory for nutrient analyses.

In vivo chlorophyll was measured with a Turner Model 111 fluorometer outfitted with a high sensitivity door, a R-136 photomultiplier and a blue 4 watt GE F4T5-B lamp. The primary filters were a Kodak 47 B and a 2A in combination and the secondary filter was a Corning CS-2-64. The *in vivo* measurements represent the fluorometer readouts as related to the most sensitive scale on the fluorometer. The data may be interpreted as a rough estimate on a relative scale of the algal standing crop.

For acetone-extractable chlorophyll, 50 ml of the sample was filtered through a RA 934 AH glass fiber filter. Two drops of a 2% slurry of magnesium carbonate were added to the sample prior to filtration. The filter was stored in a freezer for a period ranging from two days to two weeks, after which the filter was ground in 90% acetone, the slurry being adjusted to a total volume of 15 ml. After 24 hours of extraction in a refrigerator, the supernatant acetone was decanted and its fluorescence determined both before and after the addition of acid. A GE F4T4-BL lamp was used in the fluorometer and the secondary filter was changed to a Kodak 25 + 23A filter combination.

According to the procedures described by Holm-Hanson, et. al (1965), the addition of acid allows correction for phaeophytin. The fluorometric determination of chlorophyll a was calibrated using the trichromatic method as described by Creitz and Richards (1955). The chlorophyll a concentrations are expressed as mg/l of chlorophyll a in the original water sample.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Diurnal Oxygen Fluctuations

Figure 3 shows the extent of diurnal fluctuations in D.O. at three continuous water quality monitors in the study area. The plots show the range of values from maximum to minimum for each day from July 1, 1974 through September 15, 1974. The mean daily streamflows at each of the monitors are also shown.

The largest diurnal fluctuations occurred at the monitor located 2 miles downstream from Upper Sandusky (Figure 3a). At this station the D.O. dropped below 4.0 mg/l on 20 days during this period.

At St. John's Bridge, about 29 miles downstream from the monitor at Upper Sandusky, the D.O. dropped below 4.0 mg/l on 47 days (Figure 3b), according to the monitor data. The amplitude of the diurnal oxygen fluctuation at this station were much smaller than at Upper Sandusky. A possible explanation is that the intake to the monitor at St. John's Bridge is located immediately downstream from a low-headed dam. Water passing over the dam splashes on bedrock before reaching the intake, especially during the periods of low flow. The resulting aeration could reduce the amplitude of the diurnal fluctuations that may characterize the stream section above the dam. Also, measurements of D.O. in 17 grab samples collected at the monitor site gave D.O. values that averaged 2.6 mg/l higher than the average of the daily maximum D.O. reported from the monitor for the same days. The grab samples were all collected before noon so they probably did not reflect the D.O. maximum for the days. The sampling pump for the monitor pulls the water about 20 feet to the probe box. Possibly, dissolved gases are stripped from the water by the pumping system. This problem was not apparent at the other monitors.

Figure 3. Diurnal oxygen fluctuations and stream flows at three automatic water-quality monitors in the Sandusky Basin during the period from July 1 through September 15, 1974. Figure 3a, Upper Sandusky; Figure 3b, Mexico; Figure 3c, Tymochtee Creek. The maximum dissolved oxygen that the monitors record is 15 mg/l. Data are taken from Water Quality Records for Ohio, Parts I and II (U.S. Department of Interior, 1974).

At the monitor on Tymochtee Creek near Crawford (figure 3c) the D.O. dropped below 4.0 mg/l only once during the study period. It is possible that flow augmentation prevented oxygen violations at this station (see next section), since in previous years more violations have been noted. The diurnal fluctuations of D.O. in Tymochtee Creek are small in comparison to the Upper Sandusky site. Both phosphorus and chlorophyll concentrations are much lower at this location than at sites along the mainstream (Table 1). The watershed above this monitor is principally agricultural.

Flow Augmentation

When the stream flow increases at a water quality monitor, the D.O. tends to increase. Several examples of this can be seen in the graphs in figure 3. Some particularly clear cut examples can be found in earlier Water Quality Records for Ohio (U.S. Department of Interior, 1974 and earlier years) for these same stations. Although these data show the effects of natural runoff events, similar results may accompany flow augmentation.

The results of a flow augmentation "experiment" on Tymochtee Creek are shown in figure 4. On July 24, at 1200 hours a release of 30 ft³/s was initiated at Killdeer Reservoir, which is located 31 miles upstream from the water quality monitor at Crawford. The stream flow at Crawford was less than 1 ft³/s. On July 28 the flow abruptly increased to 25 ft³/s. At 800 hours the flow was still less than 1 ft³/s and at 2200 hours it was just over 25 ft³/s. It had taken approximately 96 hours for the flood front to travel the 31 miles to the gage station. Once the flood front reached the station the flow remained relatively constant for the next nine days.

Figure 4 also shows the stream conductivities as measured at the

Figure 4. Bihourly readings of streamflow and conductivity at the Crawford water quality monitor on Tymochtee Creek. Diurnal oxygen concentrations are also indicated. Data cover the period before and after the arrival of flow augmentation water released from Killdeer Reservoir. Bihourly data was supplied by the U.S. Geological Survey, Columbus, Ohio.

water quality monitor. Initially the conductivity of the stream water exceeded 1,300 μmhos . Since the conductivity of the reservoir water was only about 560 μmhos , the conductivity provided a good marker to indicate the actual arrival of water that had been stored in the reservoir. As can be seen in figure 4, significant drops in conductivity did not occur until July 31. At 1400 hours, July 30, the conductivity was still at 1,300 μmhos and not until 1800 hours, August 1, did the conductivity drop below 600 μmhos . A conductivity of 950 μmhos , which would represent about 50% stream water and 50% reservoir water, occur at 1000 hours on July 31. In traveling 31 miles the augmentation water lagged behind the flood front by about 70 hours and required a total of 166 hours to reach the monitor.

Prior to the arrival of the flow augmentation water, the minimum D.O. value had been decreasing, except for the day immediately preceding the arrival of the flood front. Unfortunately the monitor was not in operation the day the flood front arrived. The slight dip in conductivity on July 27 could indicate a light shower which could have affected the D.O. It is clear that the daily minimum D.O. values were higher after the flood front reached the station. The arrival of the water originating from the reservoir had little additional affect on the minimum D.O. values, at least through August 3. The daily maximum and minimum temperature did not change significantly during the entire period shown on the graph in figure 4. The stage rose 0.4 ft as a result of the flow augmentation.

CONCENTRATION PROFILES FOR PHOSPHORUS AND CHLOROPHYLL

Table 1 contains a summary of the results of our summer sampling program. For each of four parameters (ortho phosphorus, total phosphorus, *in vivo* chlorophyll and acetone chlorophyll) the total number of measurements (N), the mean (\bar{X}) and the standard deviation (s) are shown for each station. The values for the standard deviations are fairly large in comparison to

Table I Summary of stream water quality data obtained between June and September, 1974.

Station	Mile Point	Soluble Orthophosphate			Total Phosphorus			In Vivo Chlorophyll			Acetone Chlorophyll		
		N	\bar{X}	S	N	\bar{X}	S	N	\bar{X}	S	N	\bar{X}	S
Keiss	120.9	42	.196	.187	42	.40	.24	34	227	78	12	.06	.04
30 N B	116.6	42	.14	.11	41	.398	.234	34	425	266	13	.05	.04
Kest	114.7	44	1.44	.94	41	2.19	1.92	35	181	132	13	.02	.01
Denzer	112.4	44	1.28	.77	44	1.74	1.02	35	219	151	13	.03	.03
Shupp	109.6	44	1.24	.78	43	1.64	1.00	34	203	85	13	.03	.03
Caldwell	105.8	46	.828	.52	46	1.25	.500	35	371	274	14	.04	.02
Swartz	98.5	33	.514	.29	34	.908	.366	32	692	448	13	.08	.06
62 B	90.8	39	.273	.167	40	.576	.266	32	676	432	13	.07	.05
CR 55	86.1	41	.181	.164	42	.536	.494	34	724	439	13	.10	.08
30 N Upper	84.7	42	.153	.098	41	.402	.118	33	653	417	13	.11	.07
S-52	80.5	52	.56	.36	50	.85	.48	36	645	377	12	.11	.10
Ind Mill	78.6	42	.38	.26	42	.75	.33	34	655	376	13	.10	.04
SR 67	75.7	41	.27	.14	42	.60	.16	34	687	362	13	.12	.18
SR 103	68.7	42	.18	.30	42	.49	.16	35	822	705	13	.08	.05
S-38	66.7	41	.165	.226	41	.496	.172	33	636	334	12	.08	.05
Camp Pit	58.9	41	.123	.104	41	.378	.150	33	738	358	12	.11	.06
Hecks	55.8	41	.093	.084	42	.300	.078	34	615	516	12	.08	.05
St Johns	51.7	41	.072	.135	41	.227	.210	32	320	206	12	.05	.04
S-26	49.1	45	.082	.132	42	.198	.072	34	351	206	12	.05	.03
Ella	43.0	32	.096	.213	31	.118	.056	23	325	175	9	.05	.03
Huss	40.3	42	.076	.144	38	.198	.075	32	433	345	10	.06	.06
Township	37.5	42	.26	.20	39	.46	.22	31	451	372	9	.06	.07
Ft Seneca	32.8	41	.20	.12	39	.43	.14	31	620	427	10	.10	.08
Old Fort	27.7	43	.13	.10	40	.34	.11	31	584	410	10	.11	.08
Gilmore	25.1	40	.13	.10	39	.32	.10	31	439	417	10	.06	.04
S-10	20.5	49	.113	.09	44	.28	.09	33	378	346	10	.05	.04
Broken Swords*		40	.093	.18	37	.25	.20	32	224	71	13	.02	.02
T-20*		29	.04	.10	31	.14	.06	29	338	187	12	.05	.05
T-12*		31	.536	.321	31	.741	.404	31	169	148	11	.02	.03

* Tributary stations on Tymochtee and Broken Sword Creeks. Station 220 is at Crawford and T-12 is further downstream on Tymochtee Creek below the effluents from Carey, Ohio.

the mean values, reflecting the large variations in concentrations which characterize these parameters. Some of the variation at each station can be accounted for by variation in stream flow but much residual variation exists.

In figure 5a the mean concentrations of ortho and total phosphorus are shown as a function of river miles. The data clearly show the effects on phosphorus concentrations of both sewage treatment plant effluents and in-stream phosphorus deposition. The extremely high concentrations of phosphorus immediately below the Bucyrus sewage treatment plant reflect the low stream flow and attendant lack of dilution of plant effluent which often occurs in the Bucyrus area. The average flow of the Bucyrus sewage treatment plant is listed as 2.55 MGD ($3.95 \text{ ft}^3/\text{s}$). Table 2 summarizes the streamflow data during the study for the 4 gage stations along the river, as well as for the Tymochtee Creek stream gage.

The decreasing phosphorus concentrations with passage downstream from each town reflect deposition of phosphorus rather than dilution from tributaries with low phosphorus concentrations. This is obvious from examination of maps which show the location of tributaries. It can be proven by comparison of phosphorus fluxes rather than comparison of concentrations. From June 15 through August 7, there was an extended period without significant rainfall and surface runoff. Collections at the stream gages on 17 occasions during this period provided the opportunity to compare fluxes. The average daily flux at Upper Sandusky was 39.8 kg/day ; at Mexico, 30 kg/day ; and at Fremont 50 kg/day . The average daily stream flows at these stations during this time were: Upper Sandusky, $18.8 \text{ ft}^3/\text{s}$; Mexico, $65 \text{ ft}^3/\text{s}$; and Fremont, $79 \text{ ft}^3/\text{s}$.

The above data show that the phosphorus fluxes actually dropped

Figure 5. Profiles of mean concentrations of phosphorus and chlorophyll along the river system during June through September, 1974. Mileages shown are the distances from the mouth of the river. The three peaks in phosphorus concentration are caused by the effluents of the Bucyrus, Upper Sandusky and Tiffin sewage treatment plants. Figure 5a, phosphorus concentrations; Figure 5b, chlorophyll concentrations.

Table 2 Summary of stream flow conditions from June 1 through September 31, 1974 in the Sandusky Basin.

Stream Gage	Drainage ₂ Area, mi	Mean	Flows in ft ³ /second		Maximum
			Median	Minimum	
Bucyrus	88.8	40.5	13	3.2	795
Upper Sandusky	298	52.2	27	5.7	710
Mexico	774	93.1	74	26	790
Fremont	1,251	140.7	91	24	738*
Tymochtee**	229	5.6	2.9	0.3	30

* Excludes first 2 days in June which were on the descending side of a runoff.

** Values are greatly affected by flow augmentation.

between Upper Sandusky and Mexico even though the streamflow increased 3.5 fold. Assuming that the added streamflow contained phosphorus at the same concentration as present in agricultural tributaries, (i.e. 0.15 mg/l), the additional water would have brought in an average of 17 kg per day.

Although the average phosphorus flux at Fremont (50 kg/day) was higher than the flux at Mexico, deposition of phosphorus downstream from Tiffin is obvious from the standpoint of both concentration and flux, since the Tiffin sewage treatment plant has a listed phosphorus loading of about 62 kg/day (Ohio E.P.A., 1974). Keup (1968) and Thomann (1972) have described phosphorus deposition in rivers.

The pattern of average chlorophyll concentrations along the river (figure 5b) shows relatively high values between river mile 100 and river mile 55. A second peak shows up centered at river mile 30. The *in vivo* and acetone chlorophyll values do not mirror one another at all locations. A possible reason is that the values of both show a large amount of variation (see standard deviations in table 1) at each station and *in vivo* chlorophyll was measured much more frequently than was acetone chlorophyll.

Comparing the chlorophyll and phosphorus profiles in figure 6 indicates that in the stretch below Bucyrus, between river mile 115 and 110, the chlorophyll values were the lowest and the phosphorus highest. This merely reflects the extent of organic pollution entering from the Bucyrus sewage treatment plant. The data suggest that chlorophyll peaks are displaced downstream from the sewage treatment plants. At any particular station, plotting the individual point-pairs of phosphorus and chlorophyll give scatter diagrams showing no significant correlation between the two parameters. Comparing chlorophyll concentrations with streamflow at the stream gage sites also indicate no correlation between these two parameters

in the low flow range. Chlorophylls are low when stream flows are high.

The average chlorophyll levels do appear to be related to stream gradients along the river. Measurements taken below low head dams are much lower than those taken upstream from the dams. Detailed analyses of the chlorophyll data in relation to stream gradients, inorganic nitrogen forms, conductivities, temperatures and diurnal oxygen fluctuations have not yet been completed. As noted earlier, the diurnal fluctuations in D.O. at Crawford on Tymochtee Creek (station T-20) are much smaller than those at Upper Sandusky (station S-52). The chlorophyll concentrations are much lower at Crawford than at Upper Sandusky.

CONCLUSIONS

The data presented above suggest that the control of D.O. violations associated with diurnal fluctuations can be more effectively achieved through flow augmentation than through phosphorus removal at municipal sewage treatment plants. The effects of flow augmentation appear to be related to physical factors associated with the higher flow, rather than any chemical or biological changes that may accompany the increased flow. The latter conclusion is based on the variability of both nutrient and chlorophyll concentrations which occur within the low flow range.

Studies during the summer of 1975 should provide significant opportunities to check these conclusions. Phosphorus removal will be in operation at both Upper Sandusky and Tiffin during that summer.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors wish to thank the Soap and Detergent Association and the cities of Bucyrus, Tiffin, and Upper Sandusky for providing support for this work. The cooperation of the Ohio Environmental Protection Agency

and the U.S. Geological Survey is also greatly appreciated. Portions of the data were obtained during the operation grant Gy-11273 from the Student Oriented Program of the National Science Foundation.

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